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Research Article

**THE ROLE OF THE INTERACTION OF ELDERLY AND
YOUNG IN LIFE SATISFACTION, ADAPTABILITY AND
PROBLEM-SOLVING STYLES**Parvin Mahdavi¹, Dr.Mahboobeh Chinaveh²

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to investigate the role of elders and youth engagement in the satisfaction of life, coping and problem-solving styles among the elderly and young people in Shiraz city. A total of 160 people were selected as sample upon their availability. Index questionnaire to collect data on life satisfaction, life satisfaction scale next few teenagers, Social Adjustment Scale, and a questionnaire was used to solve the problem issues. The validity using validity and content validity and reliability was approved by. To analyze the data, descriptive statistics (mean, etc.) and inferential statistics (analysis of variance) was used. The results showed that, (1) between the satisfaction with life in seniors (elderly people who live with teens / do not) with respect to the control variables (education and income) there is a significant difference. 2. Between the two groups of seniors (seniors with teenagers living / not) combined 4 variables and problem-solving methods, there is no significant difference. 3. The adjustment in the elderly (seniors with teenagers living / not) with respect to the control variables (education and income) there is a significant difference. 4. The life satisfaction between the two groups of adolescents (teenagers who live with elderly / not) with respect to the control variables (education and income) there is a significant difference. 5. Statistically significant difference between the two groups of adolescents (teens who live with elderly / no) combined 4 variables do not exist. 6. The compatibility between the two groups of adolescents (teens who live with elderly / not) with respect to the control variables (education and income) there is a significant difference.

Keywords: Life Satisfaction, Adaptability, Problem Solving Styles, Teens, seniors**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Aging makes us all surprised. Every human being is a unique and unique entity. But when our common destiny is our own, we are often hard hit and wonder, the old age is a common destiny, and when a special and personal life We are gripping our eyes [1]. The issue of aging has, in recent years, been the focus of many of the world's minds, called 1999 as the Global Year for the Elderly. But the growing and accelerated growth of the aging population in recent years, and the great impact that this phenomenon has on social economic conditions, has provided a basis for multilateral attitudes such as social and psychological attitudes. In fact, along with the biological attitude towards the aging process The assessment of the elderly personality according to their internal changes can be paid attention to the interaction of the world outside the social behavioral approach with the aging process [2]. The opposite is the age of adolescence. In addition to change, the teenager is also equipped to face life issues, this is achieved by deciding to adopt a specific and independent situation for adults in situations that are created for him. Physiological changes and the occurrence of secondary traces and effects are not the only events of adolescence. Psychosis also occurs alongside it. Physical and mental changes change the personality of the person and his formation. As a result of such profound changes, the teenager steps into the inner world; he understands the power of thought and sets off childhood compromises [3]. Here, the presence of other people in the family, especially the grandmother's mother, can have profound effects on the various aspects of the teen's life. On the other hand, the presence of adolescents along with the elderly can be meaningful in their lives. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to examine the

interactive role of the elderly and adolescents in life satisfaction, compatibility and problem solving. Hui Goherst (1951) discourages adolescence from domination of parents and the tendency to communicate with other teenagers, the interest in choosing a job, and willingness to accept responsibility, efforts to finance and economic independence, readiness to find moral values, and Spiritual When grandparents and grandchildren often transmit information to them, they talk about activities related to the cultural heritage of the family. They narrate stories about the past and discuss family traditions and practices. The grandsons in the last decade or twenty years are increasingly becoming an important source of emotion for the elderly [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present research is a comparative causative research project that compares satisfaction, adaptability, and problem-solving styles in the elderly and adolescents who live together or not.

Statistical Society:

The statistical population of this research is all the elderly and adolescents who are covered by the family physician of the community health program in Shiraz, which consists of 4 groups, the first and second groups of elderly and adolescents living together in a common physical environment, and the third and fourth group of elderly and Teenagers who do not live together are considered.

Sample and Sampling Method:

The sample size was 160 people and the selection of people was done in one step. The sample was available from among the elderly and adolescent visitors who were present at the Health Center. From each of the above groups, 40 were selected.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Distribution of elderly and adolescent respondents by frequency and percentage

Percent	Abundance	
50	40	Older people who live with teen
50	40	Older people who do not live with teenagers
50	40	Teens who live with the elderly
50	40	Teenagers who do not live with the elderly
100	160	Total

Research tool:

The following questionnaires were used to collect information in the current research.

A) The elderly life satisfaction index (LSI) questionnaire:

Life satisfaction index (LSIA) was developed in November 1961 by Nogarin and Hoovarst, in order to assess the overall well-being of the elderly and the diagnosis of successful aging.

B) Multi-dimensional Adolescent Life Satisfaction Scale (BMSLSS) Short version:

This test is a shortened version of the Multidimensional Student Satisfaction Scale (Hoobner et al., 1994), which was developed by Hoobner et al. In 1997 to be used to identify high-risk behaviors in South Carolina.

C) Social Adjustment Questionnaire:

The Compatibility Questionnaire was developed in 1961 by Prof. Bell.

D) Problem Solving Questionnaire:

According to Heppenar and Kreskov (1987), quoted by Larson, Pentza and Vensted, 1995, the problem solving includes a series of behavioral, cognitive and emotional responses that are expressed in order to be compatible with internal and external challenges.

Analysis method:

In two levels of descriptive statistics including mean and standard deviation, multivariate analysis of variance and covariance analysis were used for inferential statistics.

Results:

Table 2: Descriptive statistics (central indicators and dispersion), relating to the elderly, according to (aged group living with adolescents / they do not)

Social adjustment	Problem Solving	Life satisfaction	elderly group	
40	40	40	Abundance	
43.85	114.48	21.35	Average	
5.798	13.119	4.780	Standard deviation	Older people who do not live with teens
52.6%	49.8%	47.1%	Total percentages	
40	40	40	Abundance	
39.55	115.25	24.00	Average	
4.044	15.338	5.875	Standard deviation	Elderly people living with teens
47.4%	50.2%	52.9%	Total percentages	
80	80	80	Abundance	
41.70	114.86	22.68	Average	
5.418	14.187	5.486	Standard deviation	Total
100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	Total percentages	

Table 3: Descriptive statistics (central indicators and dispersion), relating to adolescents, by category (adolescent group living with the elderly/ /they do not)

Social adjustment	Problem Solving	Life satisfaction	elderly group	
40	40	40	Abundance	
39.13	111.08	24.50	Average	
3.864	15.393	5.875	Standard deviation	
48.7%	49.8%	55.2%	Total percentages	
40	40	40	Abundance	
41.25	111.98	19.90	Average	
4.149	12.110	7.074	Standard deviation	
51.3%	50.2%	44.8%	Total percentages	
80	80	80	Abundance	
40.19	111.53	22.20	Average	
4.125	13.768	6.863	Standard deviation	
100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	Total percentages	

Table 4: The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to normalize the variables' observations in two groups of elderly and adolescents

Adolescent social adjustment	Solving the teens problem	Satisfaction with teen life	Social adjustment of the elderly	Solving the issue of the elderly	Satisfaction with elderly life	
80	80	80	80	80	80	Abundance
0.913	0.835	1.335	1.256	1.165	1.109	Kolmogorov-Smirnov
0.375	0.488	0.057	0.085	0.133	1710	The significance level

The distribution is normal, calculated from observations or data

Results of analyzes for inferential statistics:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant difference in life satisfaction among elderly people living with adolescents and elderly people who live alone.

Table 5: Levin test for equality of error variance for elderly life satisfaction variable

significance level	Degree of Liberty 2	Degree of Liberty 1	F
0.114	78	1	2.558

The coefficient of determination = 0.086 and the adjusted coefficient of determination=0.050

Table 7: Adjusted meanings of dependent variable. Satisfaction with life according to the elderly group

%95confidence interval		standard error	Average	Elderly group with teenagers
Highest value	Lowest value			
23.014	19.638	.848	21.326	They do not live
25.712	22.336	.848	24.024	And they live

Second hypothesis: There is a significant difference in the number of problem-solving styles among the elderly who live with adolescents and the elderly who live alone.

Table 8: Mean, standard deviation and two groups of elderly (elderly people living with adolescents/ / they do not) In the combination of variable components of problem solving styles

Number	Standard deviation	Average	The elderly group	
40	6.475	31.03	They do not live	
40	6.320	31.18	Live	Trust to solve the problem
80	6.358	31.10	Total	
40	5.990	18.25	They do not live	
40	6.778	20.83	Live	Orientation style
80	6.486	19.54	Total	
40	6.653	36.12	They do not live	
40	5.046	33.98	Live	Avoid style
80	5.966	35.05	Total	
40	4.628	21.38	They do not live	
40	4.665	20.93	And they live	Personal control
80	4.623	21.15	Total	

Table 9: of the M-BOX, homogeneity assumption of variance-covariance matrix

11.114	M-BOX value
1.050	F value
10	Degree of Liberty 1
29086.853	Degree of Liberty 2
0.398	The significance level

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION ON RESEARCH HYPOTHESES:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant difference in life satisfaction among elderly people living with adolescents and elderly people who live alone.

Based on the results of the analysis, considering that the level of significance of the group (0.028) is less than the 0.05% error rate, it is concluded that the level of life satisfaction among the elderly group (elderly with adolescents Live// they do not) Considering the control variable (educational level and income level), there is a significant difference, with respect to the average amount achieved, the life satisfaction of elderly people living with adolescents is higher than the elderly who do not live [5-8]. In order to explain this hypothesis it can be said that considering the importance of the issue of life satisfaction in the elderly and the industrialization of modern societies and the change of culture towards the maintenance of people in the elderly and the reduction of social and family support can be in satisfaction The elderly have an impact on life, so that the elderly, who are not protected and respected by their children and who are neglected by the children and placed in the nursing home, is the result of the dissatisfaction with life among the elderly. The results of the research expressed However, people with low life satisfaction are at risk of mental problems, Social and emotional such as depression, low self-concept and social interactions inappropriate. Research conducted by Korea Sugh Yong Kim in Korea shows a positive correlation between family support and life satisfaction, so that at older ages, family support is a very important factor in life satisfaction. Therefore, life satisfaction in the elderly can be improved by increasing family support. Another study showed that the attitudes of the aged children living in homes with their elderly are more positive than the attitudes of the elderly children to the elderly. Therefore, when the elderly are attended by children and are supported at home,

they are satisfied with a better life. As a result of this hypothesis, the elders who live with children or adolescents have a higher life satisfaction than themselves. Have shown.

Second hypothesis: There is a significant difference in the number of problem-solving styles among the elderly who live with adolescents and the elderly who live alone.

The results showed that there is no significant difference between the two groups of elderly people (elderly who live with adolescents) in the combination of four dependent variables.

This research is in line with Hoopman's research (2010). To explain this hypothesis we can say that when a person is faced with a situation where he cannot use the information and skills at that time to respond promptly to that position or when he has a goal and still has not found the way to Problem solving requires targeted strategies that the individual defines by means of the problem, decides to take solutions, and performs and monitors the problem-solving strategies. Identifying and applying knowledge and skills that leads to the learner's correct answer to his or her position or achievement. The basic element of solving the problem is the knowledge of the knowledge and skills previously learned in new situations, so it can be said that since the elderly, due to their age, do not have a more powerful memory and, in some cases, become obligated, they cannot have the necessary skills and expertise in the direction Solving the problem and solving problems. For this reason, problem-solving styles do not work to solve their problems.

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REFERENCES:

1. Bihhings, Diane . M.C and Stokes, Lillian . Medical – surgical Nursing. St: Louis the C.V. Mosby Co. 1987
2. McDowell, Ian (1996). Measuring health: a guide to rating scales and questions .Oxford university press. USA
3. Logan, Barbara . B. and Dawkins, Cecilia . E. Family centered nursing in the community. Massachevsets : Addison Wesley publishing Co . 1989.
4. Huebner, E. S; Suldo, S.M; Valois, R. F(2003) . Psychometric Properties of Two Brief Measures of Children's Life Satisfaction : The Student's Life Satisfaction Scale (slss) and the Brief Multidimensional student's Life Satisfaction Scale (Bmslss), University of South Carolina .
5. Edward Helmes, Richard D. Goffin and Roland D. Chrisjohn (1998). Confirmatory factor Analysis of the life satisfaction Index . Kluwer and Academic Publishers. Printed in the Netherlands .social indicators research 45: 371-390
6. Kashani JH, Rosenbery T, Beck NC, Reid JC, Battle Ef . Characteristics of well _adjusted adolescents . Canadian Journal of Psychiatry 1997 ;32 : 418 _422.
7. Lazarus, R . S. Adjustment and Personality . New York : McGraw _ Hill , 1961 .
8. Matteson, Maryann . And M.C. Connel, Eleanor . Gerontological Nursing concept and practice. W.B. Saunders Co. 1988.
9. Stanhope, Marica . And Lancaster Jeante . Community health Nursing process and practice for promoting health. Second edition, St Louis: the C.V. Mosby Co: 1988.
10. Yurick, Ann Gera . Et al . The aged person and the Nursing process. Second edition U.S.A: Appelton century crofts, 1984 .